

JURISPRUDENCE

CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY LAW IN ISLAM

Abishov S.,
teacher

Behbudov Q.,
Dr. of Philosophy in law
Nakhchivan State University

Abstract

In order to eliminate the religious and official marriage dilemma that is practiced today, the marriage must be concluded by a person who has religious characteristics. The duality in practice will be abolished, and thus, while protecting the rights of citizens, religious sensitivities will also be taken into account and legitimized by the state. The duty of the state is to ensure that both the official and religious aspects of the marriage are fulfilled by giving the imams or muftis the task of concluding the marriage. When people apply to the official institution for a marriage contract, it is of great importance to have official and religious marriages performed at the same time, if they request, in terms of both preventing grievances and legitimizing the marriage.

Keywords: family law, hadith, verse, property code, human, moral values.

Humans are the only beings that can form social relationships thanks to their ability to use their emotions and reason. As a requirement of social life, people should engage in activities such as working, producing, consuming, buying and selling, and marrying. During these activities, a person must interact with his peers. When people are engaged in such activities, they can naturally have many problems with their fellows. Although people often prefer to solve the problems they face in life with religious and moral values, they are not always successful in this. Law is the only institution that provides a final solution to the problems of individuals with each other and ensures that the rights holders get their rights. Law is a field of science that aims to solve problems between people within the framework of justice and legal principles. Jurisprudence can be defined as a set of rules that regulate a person's duty to serve his Lord, his individual behavior and his relationship with society. Therefore, if we outline the topics of fiqh in a general framework, it can be said that it consists of four main subjects: worship, the law of obligations, family law and criminal law. Marriage, which forms part of family law, has both religious and secular considerations. It is for this reason that in some of the jurisprudence works of the classical period, the issue of marriage is placed after the law of obligation, and in others, between the law of worship and the law of obligation (operation).

In general, the topics in these works follow the following order: Religion, family law, law of obligations, and criminal law. In these works, it is understood that Islamic family law is discussed immediately after prayer, that is, marriage is in a certain sense a form of worship. In the Islamic world, since the last two centuries, the term Islamic law has been used instead of the term fiqh to express the mutual rights and duties of marriage, divorce and family members. However, Islamic law is conceptually narrower in scope than jurisprudence. Because Islamic law refers to rules that regulate people's relations with society and the state, other than those related to worship. Accordingly, Islamic law generally corresponds to areas of law such as the law of

obligations, family law and criminal law. The family, which is the smallest social structure formed by people who are considered tax payers within the framework of legislation, necessitates social relations. In fact, from the day of its creation, certain rights and duties arise between family members. In short, family law can be defined as a discipline that deals with marriage, divorce and mutual rights and duties of family members.

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Islamic family law is a field of law that regulates the legal structure of the family and the rules related to the mutual rights and duties of family members with Sharia evidences such as the Holy Quran and Sunnah-Hadith. In classical fiqh books, the terms marriage and divorce were used to express all these rules, but later the words *munakahat* and *mufarakat* were used instead. Currently, independent works on Islamic family law have begun to be written. Contemporary Islamic jurists have preferred the term *al-ahwalu'sh-sahsiyyah*, which generally refers to legal situations directly related to a person's personality, i.e. personal situations, to express issues related to Islamic family law. Authors such as Abu Zehra, Abdulwahhab Hallaf and Muhammad Dusuki preferred this term.

Islamic family law; pre-marital negotiations, engagement, annulment of engagement and the legal consequences thereof; Marriage, obstacles to marriage in the part of the marriage contract, conditions related to them, legal consequences of the contract; In the divorce section, topics such as divorce, types of divorce, situa-

tions that make it possible for a woman to start a divorce case, violence caused by divorce, alimony, child care (hidane) are discussed. In this study, we have referred to the works of the classical period to determine the views of the jurists on issues related to Islamic family law. We also took advantage of the works on Islamic law written today to better understand the issue in some places. In general, we have considered the chronological sequence of sects. While giving the opinions of the schools of jurisprudence on the subject, we have mentioned the translation of the evidences (verses and hadiths) cited by the jurists of each school in the text, and the Arabic versions in the line, so as to satisfy the madhhab of the believers. providing flow of work and comfort to readers.

The Holy Qur'an states that men and women will find peace and love with the opposite sex: "One of the signs of His power is that He created for you wives of your own sex so that you may find peace and tranquility with them or with them." and that he created between you love and mercy. There are evidences for a thinking community in this." [1] This peace and love is one of the wisdoms of marriage and family life.

In Islamic Shari'ah, issues related to family law were previously expressed by the terms marriage and divorce, and later by the terms munakahat and mufarakat. Modern Islamic jurists generally use expressions such as al-ahvâlû'sh-shahsiyye or ahkâmü'l-usra for Islamic family law. The field of law that regulates mutual relations, rights and duties of family members is called family law [5]. Islamic family law includes the stages of marriage and marriage before the establishment of the family, its establishment, marriage contract, the rights and duties of the spouses after the establishment of the family, and divorce, etc. includes decisions and areas such as The concept of family is an institution that allows husband and wife to benefit from each other and live together. Just as the Qur'an states that peace, love and mercy can be achieved through family life, the Qur'an encourages people to marry: "Marry those of you who are single, and those of your maidservants and concubines who are suitable." [4]. Hz. The Prophet also encouraged Muslims to marry. He said: "O youth! He advised: "Let those of you who are able to marry marry." [4]. Again Hz. Prophet; "Marry so that you may multiply..." [5] he said. The marriage contract has many religious and secular benefits. Issues such as protecting women, ensuring their alimony, protecting the soul from adultery, and raising children in a warm home are possible only with the institution of a family established in a legal relationship. Protection of the soul from adultery is possible only on the basis of a legal relationship. Hz. According to Umar, due to the importance of marriage, "whoever marries young preserves two-thirds of his religion" [6]. "Let him fear God to protect the remaining third" [2].

In particular, the healthy growth of children, who are the guarantee of the future of humanity, is one of the most important benefits of a marriage contract. In fact, extinction is prevented by the marriage contract. However, a healthy generation is emerging.

There is continuous development and change in social life. This change, which has existed since the dawn of man, is dizzying, especially today

All these developments have also led to changes in social families. Traditions and customs are outdated and replaced by new ones. The position of women in the family and society has changed. Marriage undergoes a quiet evolution. Since it is necessary to earn more to take advantage of the conveniences provided by technology, women, along with men, have entered the working life and turned to work that generates income outside the home. Income growth boosted consumption. Earning more, consuming more, living more modestly have become passions. They have become a symbol of respect and status in society. People's goals, beliefs, value judgments, the concept of art, in short, the cultures of societies have changed [2].

Parallel to this change in social life, the rules governing social life have also changed over time. Previously, almost all the existing laws were changed according to the demand and replaced by other laws [4].

Family, which is an important part of society, is defined as an economic and social union consisting of mother, father, children and blood relatives (according to family type) [1]. The family, which is the basic and most fundamental unit of society, is one of the oldest social foundations. The first man Adam and his wife Hz. It originated with the creation of air and continues to exist to this day. In Nikah, it is a will made mutually and in accordance with each other with complete freedom of will, as provided by law, which constitutes the marriage. The parties are free to use their will in this direction. However, they must comply with the provisions of the marriage union status that occurs after using it. Accordingly, marriage is a contract formed by declaration of will of the parties. However, this contract is not similar to the type of contract accepted in the law of obligations and is a Family Law Contract subject to special forms and provisions.

The type of contract depends on the form of the marriage contract; It is not valid in the absence of formal requirements. According to the Civil Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, marriage is an official contract. The marriage ceremony is held publicly in the presence of a marriage officer and two adult witnesses, after applying to the appropriate authority in accordance with the procedure, and a necessary examination is required. The marriage officer asks each of the young people if they want to marry each other. Marriage takes place when the parties give their positive verbal responses.

In Islamic Shari'a, the fact that the marriage is performed in the presence of witnesses and the permission of the woman's parents is required for the marriage indicates that the marriage is a formal contract. In addition, due to the role played by marriage in religious and social life, attention was paid to its implementation with the participation of clergymen and lawyers who knew its legal aspects. Since marriage is a civil contract, which is mandatory for the legal establishment of a family, it has both a religious and a legal dimension. It is useful to identify these two aspects to evaluate a marriage in the process of change.

According to the rule stated in the verses and hadiths, the husband and wife who have differences of opinion do not immediately divorce, but try to solve their problems through two-way dialogue. If they cannot resolve the issue among themselves, an authorized person determined by the state body intervenes and the matter is referred to arbitrators. Arbitrators listen to the claims of both parties, act impartially, and try to resolve the conflict to the best of their ability. If the efforts of the judges do not help the continuation of the house, the judges make the most suitable decision for the parties. If it is not possible to resolve the dispute and it results in the divorce of the parties, this divorce must be registered. ‘

So, today, when examining the experts they employ and the function they perform, the Supreme Courts can be said to be performing the function of appointing judges entrusted to the state body in verse 35 of Surah Nisa. In addition, divorces are registered only by court decision. Considering that divorce is legal in cases of necessity or compulsion, it is safe to say that divorce is not halal in any dispute until the steps to be taken before

the stage of divorce in the Qur'an and the process prescribed by Islam are completed. On the other hand, since the power of divorce in our country is given to the courts by law, a unilateral divorce by a man without a court decision in official marriages should not be valid. I think this issue should be re-examined by Islamic jurists.

References

1. Holy Quran. Ziya Bunyadov and Vasim Mammadaliyev. 2001. Rum, 30/21.
2. Muhammed Ebû Zehra, al-Ahvâlû'sh-shahsiyye, Dârû'l-fikr el-Arabî, Cairo 2005, p. 19
3. Holy Quran. Ziya Bunyadov and Vasim Mammadaliyev. 2001. Nur, 24/32.
4. Ibn Majah, Abu Abdullah Muhammed b. Yezid el-Qazvini, Sunen, ed. Muhammed Nâsiru'd-Dîn al-Elbânî, Mektebetu'l-me'ârif, Riyadh, ts., "Nikâh
5. Abdürrezzak, Abu Bakr b. Hemmâm b. Nâfi' es-Sen'ânî alHimyerî, al-Musennaf fi'lhadis, thk. Habîburrahman elAzamî, First edition, Beirut 1970, VI 173.